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HOW TO SCALE UP AN ACTIVE LEARNING DESIGN FROM 50 TO 500 STUDENTS

T.H. Andersen¹

Department of Physics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Trondheim, Norway

Ø. Marøy

Department of Physics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Trondheim, Norway

G.S. Korpås

Department of Physics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Trondheim, Norway

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ABSTRACT

Over the past decade student active learning sessions have been an integrated part in some of our basic physics courses. We have used innovative learning spaces with up to 15 group stations, where each station is equipped with an interactive whiteboard connected to a computer. The students work collaboratively with both practical and theoretical exercises, using the interactive whiteboard as a joint focus. As a result of this working method the teacher has an easy access to the learning process. This kind of learning design may work well, when one teacher and an assistant facilitate the activity for 50 students. Increasing the number of students to 500 represent a challenge which may inhibit teachers to plan active learning sessions where guiding and supervision is needed.

In this paper we share how we have gone from providing weekly active learning sessions for 50 to now 500 Bachelor of Engineering students. A collaboration between four teachers and eight teaching assistants made it possible to arrange these sessions for 500 students in addition to lectures without work overload. We will describe how the teaching assistants are trained and how they take part in the design of the exercises, a context which we believe is a key element. The students were asked for their perspective on the active learning sessions in an online survey, the results of which we will share and discuss.

¹ Corresponding Author
T. H. Andersen
trine.andersen@ntnu.no

1 INTRODUCTION

The objective for using active learning as a teaching method is to have students actively taking part in constructing their own knowledge. In a definition given by Prince: *“The core elements of active learning are student activity and engagement in the learning process”* [1, p. 223], he states that active learning may refer to student activity and engagement during more traditional lectures, as a tool to prevent students from becoming passive receivers of knowledge. A more common way of implementing active learning is through collaboration, where the emphasis is on student interactions rather than learning individually [1].

We use the term active learning sessions to describe sessions where students work collaboratively and thereby learn together. To facilitate collaborative group work, innovative learning spaces with several group stations are used. Each group station is equipped with a large interactive whiteboard. The whiteboard supports and creates a joint focus for the learning process, where the dialogue between the students is essential [2,3]. To facilitate for this, the students’ tasks are designed especially for this purpose [3].

An improved understanding of concepts is enhanced through hands-on activities, as Minner et. al. says: *“having students actively think about and participate in the investigation process increases their conceptual learning. Additionally, hands-on experiences with scientific or natural phenomena also were found to be associated with increased conceptual learning”* [4, p. 493]. To have an active learning session in a lecture hall or in an ordinary classroom is possible, but to have a dedicated space that is designed for interaction and collaboration is an advantage.

The first innovative learning space at our institution was built in 2010 [5]. To support and guide the students a teacher was always present during teaching activities in this room. As long as the number of students was low, it was possible for a single teacher to manage this alone with the help of an assistant. Previously the teacher designed the exercises alone without involving the assistant. This resulted in the assistant taking a passive role during the active learning sessions, limited to answer specific questions and avoiding deeper discussions with the students.

For larger groups of students, teachers have until now refrained from having active learning sessions due to limited time and space. To increase the number of students to 500 we found it crucial to involve more teaching assistants. Based on our previous experience it is important to have enough supervisors available who also have an ownership to the exercise and can engage in discussions with the students. This led to a teamwork between four teachers and eight teaching assistants, three teachers were responsible for the lectures, while the fourth teacher and eight teaching assistants were involved in the student active learning sessions.

2 BACKGROUND

In the spring term of 2020, weekly active learning sessions for 500 students were arranged for the first time; this represented a significant up-scaling. Because of limited capacity in the innovative learning space, the 500 students were assigned to ten different time slots. Two teaching assistants were present in each of the sessions, and the 50 students were divided into groups of four to five students. In addition to the two teaching assistants the teacher responsible for the active learning sessions was usually present. The sessions were held in the innovative learning space shown in Fig. 1:

Fig. 1. The innovative learning space.

The space is equipped with several group stations, where each station has a large interactive whiteboard which is connected to a computer [5]. Here the exercises are distributed, the students do measurements, analyse data, and they write by hand on the interactive whiteboard. As well as creating a joint focus for the collaboration, the interactive whiteboard gives the teaching assistants and the teacher an easy access to the learning process [3].

The exercises consisted of practical and theoretical tasks, as well as conceptual questions for discussion. The practical exercises, as mentioned before, were developed in collaboration between the teacher and the teaching assistants during weekly meetings. Based on previous experience from active learning sessions, the teacher presented a topic and possible measurements as an inspiration and a starting point. Under guidance from the teacher, the teaching assistants engaged in a brainstorming on what to measure and how to do it. They were working hands-on using a method of trial and error, doing measurements, discussing and considering different learning aspects. To support the process the teacher asked open-ended questions. In this manner the exercise was developed, and the assistants were at the same time prepared for the discussions and questions that would likely come up during the active learning sessions. Indirectly they had also seen how to support the students by asking open-ended questions when guiding them in the learning

process. Drawing upon the experiences from this session the teacher wrote the final exercise.

The topic of the practical exercises was chosen to complement the theoretical ones by enhancing important concept and by focusing on parts of the curriculum where hands-on activities is associated with a better understanding of the physical concepts [4]. To facilitate for use of the interactive whiteboard as a joint focus, space was left open in the exercise-file for the students to share their measurements and results [3]. In the practical exercises the students had some degrees of freedom in how to do measurements and how to present the results. This is in line with the goal of increasing student engagement and interaction.

3 METHODOLOGY

To evaluate the active learning sessions an anonymous questionnaire was distributed to all students. The students were asked about how satisfied they were with the active learning sessions, indicated on a scale from 1 (not satisfied) to 5 (very satisfied). In addition to the purely quantitative response, the students were encouraged to write their qualitative perspective. The students' comments have been read by all authors through several iterations in order to agree on the interpretation and obtain a consistent view of the results. Comments included in this paper are translated into English by the authors. In total 112 of the 512 students participated, which corresponds to 22%.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical results of the questionnaire show an average of 3.7 concerning students' satisfaction. There are some differences between female and male students, while the female students are less satisfied with an average of 3.3, the male students have an average of 3.8. Fig. 2 shows the total distribution of student satisfaction:

Fig. 2. Number of students versus degree of satisfaction with the active learning sessions. Satisfaction on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is not satisfied and 5 is very satisfied.

Overall, the result shows a high degree of student satisfaction among the 112 students which answered. However, a deeper insight into students' perspective is revealed in the written comments, which we present in the following.

The purpose behind having the students collaborate and work in groups, is to encourage students' interactions. The group-work has more benefits than learning physics, as stated by this student: "*[It] creates a good learning environment where everyone (who wants) can engage*". The possibility to collaborate is acknowledged: "*It is nice to have the opportunity to collaborate, 'the effort was rewarded'*". Compared to other courses where the students worked individually, the group-work was rather unique.

Regarding the more traditional exercises in other courses, the main focus is on finding the right answer. In the active learning sessions this is not the case: "*... when we're a group we learn from each other, no one copies answers*". For several reasons copying answers is not an issue in the active learning sessions as the focus is on procedure and discussion. Each group produces their own measured values and thereby their own results. If a group needs support, the teaching assistants are there as supervisors.

An important aspect when preparing the teaching assistants for the active learning sessions was how to support and help the students. As a student pointed out: "*The teaching assistants have been very good and helpful. They have not only told us the answers if we were stuck, they 'are working with us' to find the solution.*" It is also our observation, that the teaching assistants were more active compared to earlier courses. Since the teaching assistants now take part in the design process and have already discussed the exercises, they have gained insight into thoughts and considerations concerning the assignments. We think the teaching assistants feel an "ownership" to the exercises. Through the involvement in the design process they have learned how to support the learning process themselves, by asking open-ended questions. In addition, the teacher was also supervising the students in the active learning sessions, and thereby kept acting as a role model for the teaching assistants.

Regarding the practical hands-on activities students recognise this part as valuable or even crucial for learning the concepts: "*It is a good arena for discussion, and you 'see' theory through practice*". Another student says: "*It is good to collaborate and discuss physics together, and to have practical elements that increases the understanding. However, it is difficult to go through many tasks in such large groups and one can therefore argue whether it is more effective to have individual exercises. You might get more done (tasks) in this way*". This general acknowledgement of the hands-on activities as important to increase conceptual learning is in-line with the findings in [4]. However, several students claim that they would prefer to work individually, since they feel this is a more effective way of working. The wish to work

alone might arise from the fact that this is the working method they are used to from other courses and from a belief that doing a lot of exercises gives more learning than working deeply with a few.

A related aspect mentioned by the students was the workload of the exercises. Some students were overwhelmed by the number of tasks. The intention behind the exercise was not to have the students completing all the tasks during the active learning session, but rather encourage them to focus on learning and deeper discussions. If they did not finish the exercise, they were encouraged to complete it afterwards. However, this resulted in stress for some students: *“Unfortunately, there is a time pressure to get through exercises during the session, therefore, we do not spend time discussing well enough and include everyone in the group. Physics is a subject that takes time to learn and get used to, so stressing through the exercises is not a very efficient way to learn”*. It seems, that we have not communicated well enough our intention behind the active learning sessions.

The purpose of the active learning session is for the students to learn together and construct their own knowledge. Timing is therefore important and the weekly exercises should be planned accordingly to the lecture plan, as pointed out by this student: *“[The exercise] was about the theme we just had [in the lecture], something which made us work faster with new topics”*. It is an advantage if the lecturer can relate to the activities both in the lecture before and after the active learning session. With 500 students and a space limitation of 50 it is an administrative challenge to have a well-planned time schedule for all students. Ideally the content from the active learning session should naturally fit into the theme of both the previous as well as the following lecture. This only works if all groups attending the course have their active learning sessions in between two following lectures.

We noticed that for some groups the collaboration was more difficult. Behind the average of satisfaction of 3.7 we received comments suggesting why some students are less satisfied. Comments from shortly *“I hate my group”* to the more descriptive *“The group assignment does not work, those who know – do it”*. There are several reasons that can explain this, one is keeping the same groups throughout the semester. Previously, in smaller courses, we have changed groups every week, in order not to let the groups develop “bad habits”. However, the learning management system (which is mandatory to use) does not easily allow new groups for every session. We were aware of this before starting up, however the logistics around a manually registration of 500 students each week made us go for fixed groups.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENT

To scale up an active learning design from 50 to 500 students, and still be able to support the groups during the sessions, it is crucial that the number of supervisors is scaled up as well. To do so we found it necessary to engage teaching assistants in addition to the teachers involved. Based on our experiences we acknowledge the

importance of having supervisors with an ownership to the activities. In the next run of the course it is therefore important to have the teaching assistants involved in the same way as we did now, having them engaged in developing the practical exercises.

For further improvements a better alignment between lectures and active learning sessions is preferable. This might be achieved by introducing and later giving a closure of the active learning session as part of the lectures. Another improvement is to emphasize the importance of problem solving through collaboration and discussion as an important part of practicing future engineering skills. This is something that we must communicate more clearly to the students.

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